

Attitudes of Specialists Doctors in Ramanathapuram Town

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Abstract

The study was conducted in Specialists doctors in Ramanathapuram town, to find out the views of in-patients the hospital admission process, pharmacy service, billing service, cleanliness, nursing care, and overall perception. Besides, socio-demographic characteristics of patients such as age, sex, and education-level were also including in the study. The survey was done using a structured questionnaire for a sample size of 175 outpatients, out of which 85 are male and, 90 are female patients. The researchers are mainly all ears on customer’s perception about private hospitals and how patients received and how to improve the services and are the focus for expectations development.

Keywords: Choose the hospital, Problem, Reasons for choose

Introduction

Today’s corporate hospital surroundings played on a considerable role in universal environment the final few decades have seen an outstanding development in the health and hospital perception of the Indian public environment. And they are moving out functions like Inpatients, out patients, Research and Development and Training. As well as health care sector principally corporate hospitals be played in enter role of present consumer environment like minor and major health care problems and today’s modern economic environment there are fast changes in economic empowerment in the society and various changes in the health care sector and which there has been raising the number of private hospitals and corporate hospitals and that provide health care service in both the rural and town.

Hospital is an integral part of a social and medical organization. The function of a hospital is to provide complete healthcare, both curative and preventive. The health care industry in India is becoming increasingly more competitive. There are different types of hospitals like the government hospital, private hospital, and single and multispecialty hospital, trust hospital which provide different kinds of facilities to the patients. This has necessitated each hospital to identify the functions or services which could provide a competitive edge. The products or the services in one hospital differ from another hospital. There are three categories of services such as line services, supportive services, and supporting services.

Every human being possesses the right to life and health, and the necessities of life, including proper medical services. A hospital is a

health care institution providing patient treatment by specialized staff and equipment. Hospitals are usually funded by the public sector, by health organizations (for profit or non-profit), health insurance companies, or charities, including direct charitable donations. Historically, hospitals were founded and funded by religious orders, individuals and leaders. Today, hospitals are largely staffed by professional physicians, surgeons, and nurses, whereas in the past, this work was usually performed by the founding religious orders or by volunteers.

We also consider hospital a social institution for delivering healthcare, offering considerable advantages to both patient and society. It is considered to be a place for the diagnosis and treatment of human ills and restoration of health and wellbeing of those temporarily deprived of. Above all, it is a social institution responsible for protecting the social interests, of course as a not-for-profit making organization.

The Objective of the Study

1. To study the awareness towards specialist private hospitals in Ramanathapuram town.
2. To analyze the problems of the customer in specialist private hospitals in Ramanathapuram town.

Research Methodology

Limitation of the Study

The period of the study is to (1st April 2018 to 31st August, 2018) five months. The study will be conducted to admit in different deices, and out patients.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size preferred for this study 125 respondent which including the general demographic profile of the respondents. This study has to elect Non – probability sampling methods.

Statistical Tools

In this paper has been analyzed for tools Garrett’s Ranking Technique, Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of Variation, Simple Percentage and weighted average score Analyses.

(I) Garrett’s Ranking Technique

Garrett’s ranking technique is used to identify the awareness about the specialist doctors. The patients were asked to rank some of the identified factors. This method was suggested by Garrett’s for converting the ranks into scores where the number of items ranked differed from patient to patient.

By using the following formula

$$\text{Present position} = (100(R_{ij} - 0.5)) / N_j$$

R_{ij} = Rank given for the item by the Jth individual

N_j = Total rank is given by the Jth individual

Rank	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Ranking Score	80	69	60	53	47	40	32	20

Operational Definition for Selected Specialists Doctors

Pediatrician: Specialists in the medical management of conditions affecting babies, children, and young people.

Gynecologist: Specialist in the care of the female reproductive system (the vagina, uterus, and ovaries) and the breasts.

Neurologists: Neurologists diagnosis, treatment, and care of patients with disorders of the nervous system

Dermatologist: A dermatologist is trained tars of the skin such as hair loss and scars, and the skin changes associated with aging.

General Surgery: General Surgery encompasses a wide variety of disease process and patient populations.

Ophthalmologist: An ophthalmologist has the knowledge and professional skills needed to provide comprehensive eye and vision care.

Urology: Urology is a surgical specialty that deals with diseases of the kidney and bladder of the urinary system in women and the genitourinary system (kidneys, bladder, prostate, testes, and urethra) in men.

Review of Past Studies

Jennings and Keith (2005), in their article entitled, ‘Back to the basic’ discuss the basic tents that can help healthcare marketers stay focused on their essential role and purpose within the organization. This article reveals the impact of healthcare marketing on patients, involvement of the whole organization in marketing, and applications of return on investment result for healthcare providers.

HavvaÇaha (2010), found Patients preferred private hospitals due to their belief that private hospitals provide qualitative health service in Turkey. But this did not mean that they encounter sufficient services. On the contrary, a large number of patients complain about services given by private hospitals. The complaints were mainly about the length of the time that they wait for treatment and the consultation time given to them. As a result, this study indicated that satisfaction of the patients seems to be the most important factor for the private health care providers.

Eugine Franco. C (2011), in his study “Patients’ attitude towards healthcare services provided by private hospitals in Palayamkottai” reveals that private hospitals have become highly competitive in marketing their services to the public. Further, the ever increasing number of private profit-making hospitals. It is also being witnessed that there is an inconsistency in patients’ turnout at certain private hospitals. Moreover, the study also indicates that sample patient respondents the only moderate and slight attitude towards various aspects of health care services provided by private hospitals

Maxcilla, (2014) in his research study on customer perception towards hospitals, the researcher is assessing the satisfaction of patients admitted to the hospitals. The patients are well satisfied with the responsiveness of the doctors and nurses. The study also states that patients are satisfied with the services offered by the hospitals; some patients who are mainly the general ward are dissatisfied with the sanitation and cleanliness in the toilets of the hospitals.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 Gender Classification of the Sample Patient Respondents

Sl. No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	85	47.50
2	Female	90	52.50
Total		175	100

Source: Primary Data

It could be seen from the table’s one that out of 200 respondents 52.50 percent of the respondents are Fe male and 47.50 percent of the respondents are male. This table also shows the majority of the respondents are female.

Table 2 Age-Wise Classification of Respondents

Sl. No	Age (in years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 20	21	13
2	20 to 30	41	23
3	31 to 40	51	28
4	41 to 50	32	18.5
5	Above 50	30	17.5
Total		175	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 that the age group of the respondents is divided into five groups namely below, 20, 20 to 30, 31 to 40, 41 to 50 and above 50. The researcher makes an analysis of this table 4.2, he finds that 36% of the respondents belong to the age of 20 to 30, 17% of the respondents belong to the age group of below, 31 to 40 and above 28 and the remaining 36% of the respondents belong to the age group of 41 to 50 and above 50.

Table 3 The Residential Status of the Sample Patient Respondents

Sl. No.	Area of Residence	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Rural	28	16.00
2	Urban	100	57.00
3	Semi-Urban	47	27.00
Total		175	10

Source: Primary Data

The areas an individual resides play an important role in deciding and determining the accessibility of the hospital service. Table 3 that the accessibility of the urban respondents are 57 percent and the semi-urban respondents are 27 percent and rural respondents are 16 percent.

Table 4 Education Qualification of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterate	13	7.5
2	SSLC	16	09
3	Higher secondary	20	11
4	Diploma	27	14.5
5	Graduate	44	23.5
6	Post graduate	37	19
7	Professional	29	15.5
Total		175	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 further states that 19 percent of the respondents are Post Graduate, 23.5 percent of the respondents are Graduate, 15.5 percent of the respondents are Professional, 14.5 percent of the respondents are Diploma, 11 percent of the respondents are Higher Secondary, 7.5 percent of the respondents are Illiterate and the remaining 9 percent of the respondents belong to SSLC.

Table 5 Occupation Status of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Student	33	19
2	Private employee	35	19.5
3	Govt. Employee	36	20.5
4	Farmer	20	12.5
5	Businessman	27	15.5
6	Professional	22	13
Total		175	100

Source: Primary data

Table 5 that 20.5 percent occupies by the Govt. employee, 19 percent by the Student, 19.5 percent by the Private employee, 15.5 percent by the Businessman, 12.5 percent by the Farmer, and 13 percent occupies Professional.

Table 6 Income-Wise Classification of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Monthly income	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
1	Rs.10,000 to15000	22	11
2	Rs.15,000 to 20,000	30	15
3	Rs.20,000 to 25,000	42	21
4	Rs.25,000 to 30,000	40	20
5	Rs.30,000 to 35,000	27	13.5
6	Rs.35,000 to 40,000	21	10.5
7	Rs.40,000-45,000	18	09
Total		100	

Source: Primary data

Table 6 that 26 percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between Rs10, 000 to 20,000, 41 percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between Rs20, 000 to 30, 000, Twenty-four percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between above Rs30, 000 to 40,000, and the remaining 9 percent of the respondents whose monthly income vary in between Rs 40, 000 to 45, 000.

Mean income of the respondent is Rs.27462.50, the deviation income of the respondent is Rs.8900, and the co-efficient correlation is 32.40%.

Table 7 The Awareness about the Specialist Doctors

S.No.	Patient Opinion	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Total
1	T.V/ Radio/ Advertisement	26	20	17	19	21	30	23	19	175
2	Friends/Relatives	18	16	24	29	19	27	24	18	175
3	Referred by Medical Professionals	23	16	19	28	20	06	33	30	175
4	Special Medical camp	31	26	23	21	19	25	17	13	175
5	Referred by Family doctors	21	30	22	17	18	16	22	29	175
6	Personal Relationship	20	27	25	19	26	21	17	20	175
7	Near By Home/Street	15	21	29	20	28	21	16	25	175

S.No.	Patient Opinion	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Total
8	None of the above	21	19	16	22	24	29	23	21	175
Total		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

Source: Primary data

For analyzing the benefits offered to brick workers by the brick industry, Garrett’s ranking technique has been applied.

Table 8 Garrett’s Ranking Analysis

S.No.	Reasons for Choosing The Job	Total Score	Avg. Score	Rank
1	T.V/ Radio/ Advertisement	8790	50.22	IV
2	Friends/Relatives	8622	49.26	VI
3	Referred by Medical Professionals	10564	60.36	I
4	Special Medical camp	9464	54.08	II
5	Referred by Family doctors	8741	49.94	V
6	Personal Relationship	8976	51.29	III
7	Near By Home/Street	8617	49.24	VII
8	None of the above	8561	48.92	VIII

Table 8 shows that respondents have given the first preference to Referred medical professionals, second preference Referred by Special Medical camp, Third preference to Personal Relationship, fourth preference to T,V/ Advertisement,, fifth preference to Referred by Family doctors ,Sixth rank assigned to Friends /Relatives ,Seven rank assigned to Near By Home/Street and eighth rank assigned to None of the above.

Table 9 The Patient to Select the Specialist Doctors

S. No.	Reasons	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total Score	Avg Score	Rank
		5	4	3	2	1			
1	Service for all the time	98	58	10	7	2	768	4.38	III
2	Supply in punctual services	65	81	22	4	3	726	4.14	V
3	Accessibility of trained nurses	77	41	34	9	8	677	3.86	IX
4	Sufficient infrastructure facilities	46	82	28	12	7	673	3.84	X
5	A pleasant service	23	112	15	13	12	646	3.69	XI
6	Quality treatment	61	88	18	5	3	724	4.13	VI
7	Actual Service charges	78	54	32	7	4	720	4.11	VIII
8	Hospital atmosphere	69	79	12	9	6	721	4.12	VII
9	Performance of Nurses	114	45	13	7	6	809	4.62	I
10	Performance of Doctors	95	65	10	3	2	773	4.41	II
11	Explain the Expenses in advance	55	110	5	2	3	737	4.21	IV

Source: Primary Data

From the above Table 9, it is concluded that the most number of the respondents have given first ranked for Performance of Nurse; the respondents have given the Second rank a performance of Doctors. The third rank was Service for all time; the fourth rank was explain the Expenses in advance and followed by Supply in punctual services, Quality treatment, Hospital atmosphere, Actual Service charges, Accessibility of trained nurses, sufficient infrastructure facilities, a pleasant service.

Table 10 The Problems Faced by the Consumer In Specialist Doctors

S. No.	Reasons	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total Score	Avg Score	Rank
		5	4	3	2	1			
1	High amount paid	109	57	4	3	2	793	4.53	I
2	Absences of lab services	67	89	11	3	5	735	4.20	X
3	No operation theatre	107	53	7	6	2	786	4.49	II
4	No proper communication between doctors / staff and patients	51	98	14	7	5	708	4.04	XII
5	Poor diagnosis	63	83	19	6	4	720	4.11	XI
6	Lack of basic amenities	78	81	11	2	3	754	4.30	IV
7	Lack of basic amenities	98	52	13	4	8	752	4.29	V
8	Absences of new technology and equipment	83	62	18	8	4	737	4.21	IX
9	Long queue for consulting, getting an x-ray, scanning etc.,	73	81	12	5	4	739	4.22	VII
10	Insufficient visits of senior doctors	88	61	13	6	7	742	4.24	VII
11	A limited number of beds	83	75	10	3	4	755	4.31	III
12	Lack of privacy of patients and poor facility of waiting rooms	43	102	16	9	5	694	3.96	XIII
13	Insufficient ambulance facility	53	104	15	8	5	747	4.26	VI

Source: Primary Data

From the above Table 10, it is concluded that the most number of the respondents have given first ranked for High amount paid; the respondent have given the second rank for No operation theatre. The third rank was a limited number of beds, fourth rank was Lack of basic amenities and followed by No proper consulting time, insufficient ambulance facility, Insufficient visits of senior doctors, Long queue for consulting, getting an X-ray, scanning, etc. Absences of new technology and equipments, No proper communication between doctors / staff and patients and No proper consulting time, Absences of lab services, Poor diagnosis, No proper communication between doctors/staff and patients, Lack of privacy of patients and poor facility of waiting rooms.

Suggestion

1. Today's modern hospital's environment provides all the possible medical care under within the one roof with reasonable cost.
2. The specialist doctors keep or maintain their service quality is an important aspect for the customers.

Conclusion

This study reveals that people generally prefer specialist doctors when they talk about timeliness, infrastructure, before and after time services, extra care, advance techniques, etc. Hospitals industry today plays a big role in making the welfare of the public. Doctors come second after God. So both organization should take care of their social responsibility towards the society first and profit afterward. Therefore, it is concluded that providing quality health care service at an affordable cost has become not only the need of the hour but also the order of the day.

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